

VENTURE CAPITAL AND INNOVATION – THE INDIAN EXPERIENCE

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Introduction:

Venture Capital (VC) is a significant financial innovation in the twentieth century. It is a form of financing, designed for funding high technology with high risk and with perceived high rewards. It usually refers to financing provided by venture capitalists, who invest, alongside innovative entrepreneurs, in relatively new, high growth companies that have a reasonable, though not assured, potential to develop into highly profitable ventures. Such investments may exhibit high-risk (of failure) or high return (in terms of large appreciation in the capital invested) characteristics.

Venture Capital Environment in India:

The development of venture capital is a recent phenomenon in India. It is still in its infancy stage and requires proper framework and promotional efforts for its fast growth. With a view to promote scientific innovations into technology and knowledge-based ideas into commercial production, it is very important to promote venture capital activity in India. India’s recent success story in the area of information technology has shown that there is a tremendous potential for the growth of knowledge-based industries. This potential is not only confined to information technology but is equally relevant in several areas such as bio-technology, pharmaceuticals and drugs, agriculture, food processing, telecommunications, services and the like. Given the inherent strength by way of its skilled and cost-competitive manpower, technology, research and entrepreneurship, with proper environment and policy support, India can achieve rapid economic growth and competitive global strength in a sustainable manner.

Indian Venture Capital Scenario:

In India Venture Capital plays a vital role in the development and growth of innovative entrepreneurship. Venture Capital activity in the past was possibly done by the developmental financial institutions like IDBI, ICICI and State Financial Corporations. But VC financing was really started in India during 1988 with the formation of Technology Development and Information Company of India Ltd. (TDICI) - promoted by ICICI and UTI. At the same time Gujarat Venture Finance Ltd. and APIDC Venture Capital Ltd. have been started by the state level financial institutions. These funds have been sourced from the financial institutions, foreign institutional investors or pension funds and high net-worth individuals.

Gujarat Venture Capital Fund:

In the year 1990, Gujarat Venture Finance Limited (GVFL) began its operations with the investments from World Bank, U.K Common Wealth Development Fund, Gujarat Industrial Investment Corporation, Industrial Development Bank of India, various other banks, state corporations and private firms. The success of GVFL has resulted in launching of its second fund, Gujarat venture Capital Fund on 17th January, 1995 with a corpus of Rs.60 crore. The fund has provided assistance in the form of equity, convertible preference shares and convertible debentures. The distribution of investment instruments has been:

Instrument	Amount (Rs. Crore)
Equity	15.81
Convertible preference shares	3.28
Convertible debts	5.00
Total	24.09

The fund has provided assistance to 14 companies out of which 4 Public Ltd. companies have been selected for the study:

- ✓ Akshay Software Technologies Limited – The Company was incorporated in the year 1987 it deals with Turnkey Software Projects and Generic Software products.
- ✓ Computer skill Limited – The Company was incorporated in the year 1987 it deals with Specialized Printing and packing.
- ✓ 20 Microns limited – The Company was incorporated in the year 1987 it deals with micronized minerals.
- ✓ Broadcast Worldwide Limited – The Company was incorporated in the year 1999 it is a Regional TV Channel.

Importance of the Study:

The recent thrust on globalization and encouraging linkage between India and the world economies have opened up new avenues in financial services market. The prospects for the Industrial finance and

particularly venture capital finance are very high. This in turn will have a consequential effect on the volume of venture capital assistance required to finance the growth in industrial sector. In view of this excellent growth potential of venture capital firms in India, a study has been felt necessary to know about the operational ability of some of the select venture capital beneficiaries of Gujarat venture finance Ltd.

Objectives of the Study:

- The study has been undertaken keeping in mind the following objectives:
- ✓ To highlight the growth potential for Venture Capital in India.
 - ✓ To study and evaluate the operational ability of select venture capital beneficiaries of Gujarat venture capital fund.

Research Methodology:

The study has been analytical in nature and for the purpose of the study four public limited companies those who have enjoyed the venture funds provided by Gujarat venture capital fund 1995 have been chosen and assessed for their financial performance for five years from 2012-2016. The data has been sourced from secondary sources such as books, magazines, journals, CMIE (Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy) database and through internet. Relevant statistical tools such as mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation and linear growth rate have been applied to analyze the data.

Review of Literature

A few of the reviews relating to Venture Capital have been recorded here under:

Huntsman & Hoban, (1990)¹, in their research paper on “Investment in new enterprise – Some empirical observations on risk, return and capital market structure”, have examined 110 investments by three venture capital firms over a period of 15 years from 1960 to 1975 to study the risk and return of investments made in new enterprises. Although they have not provided a formal test of their returns they concluded that the success of venture capital investments have highly depended on finding a few outstanding investments and diversifications as vital for the success of a firm.

I. M. Pandey, (1999)², his article on “Venture Capital in India” has stated that in general venture capital has been considered as a synonym of high risk capital, that has been long term funds invested in new enterprises. In broad terms, the author has described venture capital as the investment of long-term risk equity finance where the primary reward for the venture capitalists has been an eventual capital gain. More often venture capital would be a commitment of capital or shareholdings for the formation and setting up of small companies specializing in new ideas and new technologies.

Mishra, A. K, (2013)³, his developmental approach to venture capital financing has claimed that the concept of venture capital first began in United States of America and spread throughout the world by mid-seventies. In India, it came later when the entrepreneurs confronted financial constraints on account of difficulties in raising funds. The government has decided to promote venture capital for boosting industrial development. It has announced guidelines and over the counter market and made it essential for government and venture capital companies to review and resolve the issues that could come in the way of the growth of their industry on secured and professional lines.

Analysis and Findings:

The following table no. 1 to 9 has analysed the financial performance of the select venture capital investee companies and the results have been displayed below:

Table 1: Liquidity Ratios

Company Name	Year	Quick Ratio	Current Ratio	ALR
20 Microns Ltd.	2012	0.777	1.426	0.213
	2013	0.868	1.442	0.207
	2014	0.913	1.440	0.368
	2015	0.882	1.450	0.368
	2016	0.828	1.388	0.422
	Mean	0.85	1.43	0.32
	S.D	0.05	0.02	0.10
	C.V	6.15	1.72	31.36
	LGR	0.01	-0.01	0.06
Akshay Software Technologies Ltd.	2012	1.126	1.413	0.323
	2013	1.269	1.600	0.457
	2014	1.366	1.813	0.419
	2015	1.263	1.408	0.372
	2016	1.811	1.986	0.972
	Mean	1.37	1.64	0.51
	S.D	0.26	0.25	0.26
	C.V	19.20	15.43	51.92
	LGR	0.14	0.10	0.12
Broadcast	2012	0.249	0.401	0.174

Worldwide Ltd.				
	2013	0.497	0.869	0.204
	2014	0.470	1.077	0.252
	2015	0.559	1.087	0.392
	2016	1.145	1.679	0.927
	Mean	0.58	1.02	0.39
	S.D	0.33	0.46	0.31
	C.V	57.28	45.03	79.98
	LGR	0.19	0.28	0.17
Computer Skill Ltd.	2012	0.831	1.853	0.623
	2013	1.106	2.251	0.404
	2014	0.891	1.586	0.357
	2015	0.484	1.182	0.186
	2016	0.249	0.954	0.153
	Mean	0.71	1.57	0.34
	S.D	0.34	0.52	0.19
	C.V	47.99	33.10	54.95
	LGR	-0.18	-0.29	-0.12

Source: Computed

Akshay Software Technologies Ltd. has maintained a better liquidity position as compared to other companies. Its Current ratio has increased from 1.413 in the year 2012 to 1.986 in the year 2016 similarly its liquid ratio and Absolute liquid ratios are also showing an increasing trend. 20 Microns Ltd. has the next best to Akshay Software Technologies Ltd. among the four companies chosen followed by Computer skill Ltd. and Broadcast Worldwide Ltd.

Table 2: Turnover Ratios

Company Name	Year	Debtors Turnover	Creditors Turnover	Inventory Turnover
20 Microns Ltd.	2012	4.222	4.341	4.005
	2013	5.681	5.576	5.372
	2014	7.697	7.101	7.156
	2015	7.508	9.177	6.952
	2016	6.711	8.874	6.291
	Mean	6.36	7.01	5.96
	S.D	1.44	2.08	1.29
	C.V	22.58	29.70	21.72
	LGR	0.68	1.27	0.62
Akshay Software Technologies Ltd.	2012	-	-	-
	2013	3.980	6.122	3.757
	2014	3.968	5.687	3.744
	2015	4.715	5.061	4.563
	2016	5.868	5.810	5.465
	Mean	4.63	5.67	4.38
	S.D	0.89	0.45	0.82
	C.V	19.31	7.86	18.65
	LGR	0.64	-0.16	0.59
Broadcast Worldwide Ltd.	2012	-	-	-
	2013	3.927	0.564	3.299
	2014	3.490	0.909	3.258
	2015	4.765	1.671	4.535
	2016	7.088	1.604	6.033
	Mean	4.82	1.19	4.28
	S.D	1.60	0.54	1.31
	C.V	33.28	45.46	30.59
	LGR	1.08	0.39	0.95
Computer Skill Ltd.	2012	2.844	5.127	2.630
	2013	1.975	4.879	1.814
	2014	1.494	4.144	1.875
	2015	2.668	6.877	2.874
	2016	0.455	0.968	0.769
	Mean	1.89	4.40	1.99
	S.D	0.97	2.16	0.83
	C.V	51.23	49.20	41.43
	LGR	-0.41	-0.63	-0.27

Source: Computed

20 Microns Ltd. has had greater turnover ratios as compared to the other three companies chosen and Akshay Software Technologies Ltd. has had a fairly moderate turnover ratio for the given period. However the inventory turnover has been highly favorable for 20 Microns Ltd. and Computer Skill Ltd. due to higher levels of production and the turnover from the creditors.

Table 3: Net Working Capital Cycle

Company Name	Year	Net Working Capital Cycle	Debtors (ACP)	Creditors (APP)
20 Microns Ltd.	2012	200.341	86.462	58.530
	2013	110.754	64.252	50.428
	2014	86.629	47.423	38.310
	2015	102.519	48.616	35.075
	2016	118.130	54.389	40.113
	Mean	123.67	60.23	44.49
	S.D	44.43	16.10	9.73
	C.V	35.92	26.74	21.86
	LGR	-17.27	-7.98	-5.22
Akshay Software Technologies Ltd.	2012	-	-	113.166
	2013	37.339	91.715	54.376
	2014	31.897	91.985	60.088
	2015	-0.660	77.409	78.069
	2016	18.666	62.202	43.536
	Mean	21.81	80.83	69.85
	S.D	16.91	14.16	27.25
	C.V	77.52	17.52	39.02
	LGR	-8.86	-10.31	-11.56
Broadcast Worldwide Ltd.	2012	-	-	544.375
	2013	-136.983	92.948	260.300
	2014	-42.289	104.579	179.170
	2015	-48.820	76.608	151.748
	2016	-55.455	51.499	128.807
	Mean	-70.89	81.41	252.88
	S.D	44.39	23.00	170.35
	C.V	-62.62	28.26	67.36
	LGR	23.81	-15.23	-93.97
Computer Skill Ltd.	2012	264.402	128.356	61.040
	2013	313.692	184.789	132.803
	2014	6.494	244.338	404.702
	2015	9.544	136.797	237.035
	2016	-110.397	802.681	1333.288
	Mean	96.75	299.39	433.77
	S.D	182.92	285.11	519.18
	C.V	189.07	95.23	119.69
	LGR	-105.37	130.07	264.87

Source: Computed

Broadcast worldwide Ltd. has a high status with respect to the Net Working Capital cycle. Where the Average Payment Period is highly favorable as compared to the Average Collection Period. 20 Microns Ltd. has posted the lowest liquidity and Akshay Software Technologies Ltd. with Computer Skill Ltd have shown a remarkable improvement in their Net Working Capital cycle.

Table 4: Profitability on Sales

Company Name	Year	PBIT Net of PE & OI/Sales	PBT Net of PE & OI/Sales	PAT Net of PE & OI/Sales	Cash profit Net of PE & OI/Sales
20 Microns Ltd.	2012	-4.985	-11.807	-10.045	3.654
	2013	-5.101	-11.084	-11.136	5.862
	2014	6.659	1.512	2.580	5.896
	2015	9.447	4.991	3.835	5.131
	2016	10.001	5.750	3.267	6.551
	Mean	3.20	-2.13	-2.30	5.42
	S.D	7.63	8.66	7.59	1.11
	C.V	238.27	-406.98	-330.08	20.43
	LGR	4.45	5.12	4.16	0.51
Akshay Software Technologies Ltd.	2012	8.000	5.091	5.091	10.909
	2013	7.810	5.942	4.584	6.112

	2014	6.924	5.475	4.670	6.119
	2015	4.295	3.221	2.282	3.087
	2016	6.862	6.187	4.949	5.399
	Mean	6.78	5.18	4.32	6.33
	S.D	1.48	1.18	1.16	2.85
	C.V	21.82	22.67	26.77	45.02
	LGR	-0.58	-0.05	-0.26	-1.40
Broadcast Worldwide Ltd.	2012	5.337	-18.820	-19.007	25.843
	2013	15.144	3.638	3.638	16.413
	2014	11.311	3.221	2.846	7.416
	2015	8.793	1.861	1.155	7.317
	2016	18.218	11.207	9.885	13.908
	Mean	11.76	0.22	-0.30	14.18
	S.D	5.08	11.25	10.97	7.65
	C.V	43.23	5083.60	-3698.67	53.93
	LGR	1.94	5.83	5.53	-3.30
Computer Skill Ltd.	2012	11.440	-3.171	-3.675	8.091
	2013	8.779	-5.614	-3.434	6.271
	2014	-23.582	-41.996	-46.195	-25.305
	2015	-26.003	-37.468	-35.717	-12.276
	2016	-101.124	-161.298	-161.423	-91.261
	Mean	-26.10	-49.91	-50.09	-22.90
	S.D	45.44	64.75	65.09	40.63
	C.V	-174.13	-129.74	-129.95	-177.46
	LGR	-25.99	-34.81	-34.78	-21.73

Source: Computed

Akshay Software Technologies Ltd. has all along been profitable during the 5 years period showing the financial strength that it had built with the venture capital raised as compared to the other three companies.

Table 5: Profitability on Networth

Company Name	Year	PBIT Net of P&E/ Avg. net worth	PAT Net of P&E/ Avg. net worth	PAT/Avg. net worth	Cash profit /Avg. net worth
20 Microns Ltd.	2012	-9.615	-19.375	-21.977	4.446
	2013	-13.501	-29.474	-28.924	16.064
	2014	24.691	9.568	9.259	21.553
	2015	40.137	16.291	16.246	21.752
	2016	43.985	14.368	17.586	27.433
	Mean	17.14	-1.72	-1.56	18.25
	S.D	27.21	21.17	22.17	8.70
	C.V	158.75	-1227.73	-1419.36	47.68
	LGR	16.08	11.32	12.43	5.17
Akshay Software Technologies Ltd.	2012	-	-	-	-
	2013	3.315	1.946	1.874	2.523
	2014	3.039	2.049	2.049	2.686
	2015	2.226	1.183	1.043	0.557
	2016	4.165	3.004	2.595	2.868
	Mean	3.19	2.05	1.89	2.16
	S.D	0.80	0.75	0.64	1.08
	C.V	25.10	36.52	33.99	49.90
	LGR	0.17	0.23	0.12	-0.11
Broadcast Worldwide Ltd.	2012	-	-	-	-
	2013	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	2014	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	2015	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	2016	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Mean	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	S.D	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	C.V	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	LGR	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Computer Skill Ltd.	2012	19.629	-6.306	3.966	13.883
	2013	13.897	-5.436	-4.254	11.723
	2014	-57.031	-111.719	-197.830	-61.979
	2015	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

	2016	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Mean	-4.70	-24.69	-39.62	-7.27
	S.D	30.50	48.74	88.49	31.25
	C.V	-648.75	-197.39	-223.32	-429.61
	LGR	-5.32	1.80	-0.37	-3.95

Source: Computed

Networth of a company indicates the shareholders' funds. A high profitability on networth maximizes the wealth of a concern. Akshay Software Technologies Ltd. has recorded consistent profitability on its networth showing its ability to maximize its shareholders wealth. 20 Microns Ltd. has gathered sufficient strength after 2012. The Broadcast Worldwide Ltd. and Computer skill Ltd. have not been in a position to post profits.

Table 6: Profitability on Capital Employed

Company Name	Year	PBIT Net of P&E/ Avg. Capital Employed	PBT/Avg. Capital Employed	PAT Net of P&E/Avg. Capital Employed	PAT/ Avg. Capital Employed
20 Microns Ltd.	2012	-4.860	-6.176	-9.794	-11.109
	2013	-5.571	-5.344	-12.161	-11.935
	2014	9.141	9.027	3.542	3.428
	2015	16.299	16.280	6.616	6.597
	2016	20.263	21.746	6.619	8.102
	Mean	7.05	7.11	-1.04	-0.98
	S.D	11.89	12.59	9.20	9.77
	C.V	168.57	177.10	-888.38	-993.62
	LGR	7.21	7.75	5.16	5.70
Akshay Software Technologies Ltd.	2012	-	-	-	-
	2013	3.198	3.128	1.877	1.807
	2014	2.953	2.953	1.992	1.992
	2015	2.172	2.037	1.154	1.018
	2016	4.076	3.675	2.940	2.539
	Mean	3.10	2.95	1.99	1.84
	S.D	0.78	0.68	0.73	0.63
	C.V	25.29	23.10	36.85	34.22
	LGR	0.19	0.07	0.24	0.12
Broadcast Worldwide Ltd.	2012	-	-	-	-
	2013	675.472	1573.585	162.264	1060.377
	2014	40.374	67.112	10.160	36.898
	2015	28.995	38.942	3.810	13.757
	2016	45.092	77.952	24.467	57.326
	Mean	197.48	439.40	50.18	292.09
	S.D	318.73	756.30	75.22	512.50
	C.V	161.40	172.12	149.92	175.46
	LGR	-190.25	-451.51	-41.97	-303.23
Computer Skill Ltd.	2012	8.621	13.132	-2.769	1.742
	2013	6.267	6.800	-2.451	-1.918
	2014	-16.056	-40.298	-31.452	-55.694
	2015	-50.310	-53.779	-69.104	-72.573
	2016	-76.705	-79.072	-122.443	-124.811
	Mean	-25.64	-30.64	-45.64	-50.65
	S.D	37.08	39.66	50.88	52.74
	C.V	-144.64	-129.43	-111.46	-104.12
	LGR	-22.72	-24.50	-30.60	-32.38

Source: Computed

Though Broadcast worldwide Ltd. had posted huge profits during the year 2013, it had suffered a heavy drop in profits during 2014-15. Thereafter it has been able to utilize the venture capital profitably from 2016. Akshay Software Technologies on the other hand has been maintaining a consistent performance with an increase in its rate of return on capital employed by twice the previous year's figures. 20 Microns Ltd. though having teething problem during 2012-13, has picked up in its rate of return on capital employed during the subsequent years.

Table 7: Profitability on Total Assets

Company Name	Year	PBIT Net of P&E/Avg. Total Assets	PBIT/Avg. Total Assets	PAT Net of P&E/Avg. Total Assets	PAT/Avg. Total Assets
20 Microns Ltd.	2012	-3.300	-4.194	-6.650	-7.543
	2013	-4.033	-3.869	-8.804	-8.640
	2014	6.665	6.582	2.583	2.499

	2015	11.129	11.117	4.517	4.505
	2016	12.614	13.537	4.120	5.043
	Mean	4.62	4.63	-0.85	-0.83
	S.D	7.87	8.30	6.37	6.71
	C.V	170.63	179.00	-752.11	-811.27
	LGR	4.70	5.04	3.49	3.83
Akshay Software Technologies Ltd.	2012	-	-	-	-
	2013	2.919	2.855	1.713	1.650
	2014	2.705	2.705	1.824	1.824
	2015	1.961	1.839	1.042	0.919
	2016	3.665	3.304	2.643	2.283
	Mean	2.81	2.68	1.81	1.67
	S.D	0.70	0.61	0.66	0.57
	C.V	24.92	22.92	36.37	33.95
	LGR	0.15	0.05	0.20	0.10
Broadcast Worldwide Ltd.	2012	-	-	-	-
	2013	18.340	42.725	4.406	28.791
	2014	14.526	24.146	3.656	13.276
	2015	12.449	16.720	1.636	5.906
	2016	24.564	42.464	13.328	31.228
	Mean	17.47	31.51	5.76	19.80
	S.D	5.32	13.15	5.18	12.21
	C.V	30.46	41.73	90.02	61.65
	LGR	1.66	-0.82	2.47	-0.01
Computer Skill Ltd.	2012	6.183	9.419	-1.986	1.249
	2013	4.416	4.792	-1.727	-1.352
	2014	-8.786	-22.051	-17.210	-30.476
	2015	-16.980	-18.151	-23.324	-24.495
	2016	-12.955	-13.355	-20.680	-21.080
	Mean	-5.62	-7.87	-12.99	-15.23
	S.D	10.40	14.11	10.39	14.29
	C.V	-184.97	-179.27	-80.00	-93.82
	LGR	-5.97	-6.85	-5.90	-6.78

Source: Computed

Broadcast worldwide Ltd and Akshay Software Technologies Ltd. have shown consistently a compatible usage of venture capital in their investment patterns and in the profits realization from the utilization of assets. 20 Microns Ltd., though suffering from the initial problem, had picked up its return rate after 2014. The Computer Skill Ltd. has suffered lack of technological support to wipe off its earlier drawbacks, and should be in a position to step into the road of recovery in the following years.

Debt- Equity & Interest Cover Ratio:

The beneficiaries of Gujarat Venture Capital Fund 1995 have enjoyed an interest cover from their return to have a surplus to maximize their shareholders wealth.

Table 8: Debt- Equity & Interest Cover Ratio

Year	2012		2013		2014		2015		2016	
	Debt Equity	Interest Cover								
20 Microns Ltd.	1.55	-0.73	2.08	-0.85	1.97	1.29	1.78	2.12	1.63	2.35
Akshay Software Technologies Ltd.	0.07	2.75	0.05	4.18	0.04	4.77	0.03	4	0.04	10.16
Broadcast Worldwide Ltd.	-	0.22	-	1.31	-	1.39	-	1.26	-	2.59
Computer Skill Ltd.	1.677	0.78	1.63	0.60	-	1.28	-	2.26	-	1.68

Source: Computed

The 2 companies that have leveraged completely their wealth with debt capital have been Akshay Software technologies Ltd. first and 20 Microns Ltd. second. Akshay Software Technologies Ltd. has posted even 4 times profits while 20 Microns Ltd. has posted twice the interest coverage as profits. Broadcast Worldwide Ltd. has not leveraged its capital though has had initial leveraging and has redeemed its debts during 2014.

Table 9: Reserves & Surplus and Paid up Equity Capital

Year	2012		2013		2014		2015		2016	
	Reserves & Surplus	Paid up Equity Capital	Reserves & Surplus	Paid up Equity Capital	Reserves & Surplus	Paid up Equity Capital	Reserves & Surplus	Paid up Equity Capital	Reserves & Surplus	Paid up Equity Capital
Company Name										

20 Microns Ltd.	12.57	12.44	6.25	12.44	7.75	12.44	11.32	12.44	16	12.44
Akshay Software Technologies Ltd.	9.05	4.7	9.3	4.7	9.6	4.7	9.75	4.7	10.14	4.7
Broadcast Worldwide Ltd.	-40.97	23.15	-38.16	23.15	36.78	23.15	-36.13	23.15	32.11	29.15
Computer Skill Ltd.	11.09	7.77	11.2	9.81	-11.58	10.43	-29.15	10.43	-42	10.43

Source: Computed

It is heartening to note that 20 Microns Ltd. and Akshay Software Technologies Ltd. have managed even to build up their reserves more than or equal to their paid up equity and will turnout in the next year as bonus candidates. With an extra technical assistance, Broadcast Worldwide Ltd. and Computer Skill Ltd. will also be able to trot on the path of profitability in the near future.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Proper awareness of venture capital activity is important for its development. Lack of social awareness of the existence of venture capital industry has been observed. Hardly a few know about the principal objectives and functions of the existing venture capital funds in the country and thus backing of the media is required to bridge the gap between the society and the existing venture capital funds. One immediate measure could be the creation of an informed website which could have sufficient and useful data on venture capital activity.
- ✓ In India there is no dearth of creativity, though it is little used. Venture capitalists should provide the entrepreneur moral support in forming the company besides financial and technical support. Finally, they should play the role of a partner and manager rather than just a financier.

Conclusion:

In India, institutionalization of finance for new opportunities and ventures in the form of venture capital has no doubt accelerated the investment process. However, there are bottlenecks that have to be overcome before venture financing can be set on a firm footing in India. The present constraints are mostly environmental, and could be eliminated through policy measures. It is now essential for the government and the venture capital companies to review and resolve the issues that could come in the way of growth of this industry, on sound professional lines. The sample companies have proved that the venture capital as a source of fund can certainly benefit in the industrial growth and in the economic prosperity of the country at large.

References:

1. Huntsman, B and Hoban J.P., "Investment in new enterprise: Some empirical observations on risk, return and market structure", *Financial Management*, 1990, Vol. 9, pp. 44-51.
2. I. M. Pandey, "Venture Capital in India", *Chartered Financial Analyst*, July-August, 1999 pp.84-98.
3. Mishra, A. K., "Venture Capital financing: Evaluation studies and follow-up action", *Chartered Accountant*, 2013, pp.361-367.
4. Venture capital in India- Satish Taneja.
5. Pankaj sahai, "What's on the VC's Mind?" *Intelligent Investor*, March 15, 2001.
6. SEBI Guidelines for Venture Capital.
7. Venture Capital Financing in India"- Mishra A.K
8. www.money control.com